

**CURRENT TRENDS IN EDUCATION AND IMPACT ON PUBLIC LIBRARY
MANAGEMENT JAGDISHMAL JHABARMAL TIBREWALA
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Abstract:

This paper tends to focus on the different types of learning methods. With this changing scenario of learning methods from classroom to distance learning. The role of public library professionals also changing with these developments. Now the information is available everywhere, anytime in different formats, but the library professionals have to play a role of refries as like a referral managers. LIS professional's acquaintance with new technology is the area of survivals. In this changing scenario library professionals have to show their potentials and convey the management authorities.

Key Words: *Modern Learning Methods, Role of Information and Communication Technology, Library Information Science.*

Introduction:

The use of classroom teaching took place in to the virtual classroom. The innovation in ICT has spread all over in the world. Interactive learning methods have been increased and the concept of resource sharing and Networking in the libraries enhanced. Till now after all developments in ICT have not made every information available. There is a need of human interference. Present learning methods can be categories as under.

CLASSROOM LEARNING:

Now a days classroom learning methods have been changing. The use of LCD and different types of presentation skills has been used. Role of teachers also changing, instead of blackboard the use of LCD screen are increased. The Audio Visual Media has proved to be more effective than the blackboard and has enhanced the retention and reproduction of the learning in the students. Enhanced learning techniques like Buzan's Techniques have been introduced in the classroom as a result of Audio Visual Media. This has also helped the classroom teaching to be more interactive.

E-LEARNING:

Electronic learning (e-learning) is a general term used to refer to computer enhanced learning. It is commonly associated with the field of Advanced Learning Technology, which deals with both the technologies and associated methodologies in learning using networked and/or multimedia technologies. This is the fastest growing learning methods of all and has contributed towards learning additional skills. More and more universities are adding e-learning as a method of teaching.

U-LEARNING:

U-Learning means "everywhere learning" with the help of various devices plug in and retrieve the information in the appropriate format (PDA, Cell phone, laptop, or any other technology gadgets). It fulfills e-learning's promise of "anytime, anywhere and any context". This has almost revolutionized the learning and as communication technology is growing this kind of learning will be more popular. The major advantage of this kind of learning is the flexibility of timing and place.

BLENDED LEARNING:

Hybrid learning, sometimes called "Blended Learning", provides the best opportunities for learning transition from classroom to e-learning. It provide students with an option of taking some learning materials fully online and some in class, or hybrid. These methods may include a mixture of face-to-face classrooms, self-paced learning and online classrooms. With Cloud computing becoming popular this kind of learning will become more popular as the e-learning and classroom lecture videos would be accessed through the cloud. The major

challenge in this method is the internet bandwidth which is required to access the e-learning lectures and videos.

DISTANCE LEARNING:

It is a type of learning with the study material provided by the Open Universities. While self-study by students have counseling sessions to get their doubts clarifications. Mode of learning can be used via e-mail, electronic forums, video conferencing, chat rooms, instant messaging and other forms of computer-based communication. These are the present methods of learning, libraries have support the learners as well as the teachers. Librarians have to develop their professional competencies. They have to deal with information technology skills by handling hardware/software systems, Database creation is the one more skill, and user's surveys are required to know their information needs. Collection of online databases can be a strengthening awareness of users.

DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES.

- Developing effective team-relationship
- Coping with latest technological changes
- Training library professionals with technology
- Up-dation of databases
- Timely decision making and problem solving attitude
- Optimum utilization of available resources and keeping rapport with management
- Developing library service marketing and presentation skills
- Developing knowledge mapping skills
- Developing effective communication skills
- Developing ICT infrastructure
- Outsourcing of library services
- Developing library co-operation to resource sharing

- Joining library consortia
- Collection development

Application of different types of management techniques like SWOT Analysis , TQM, Six Sigma, Proper time management. LIS professionals have to visualize future directions and prepare a roadmap to provide the most effective and efficient library and information services to the users. Improvement in information seeking habits and updating our end users. To know the information needs of the users accordingly collection of information, proper organization of information, timely dissemination of information will keep users attachment.

CONCLUSION:

Today in the field of education different types of learning methods evolved. As per the change in the learning style, the changes in library services and management would be essential. Hence the significantly it is the high time for the LIS professionals to get awareness of these ICT changes for their future growth.

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